

Molecular triggers of post-COVID-19 parosmia in grilled chicken

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Abstract

Since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, incidences of loss of smell and taste have increased substantially and, whereas many of these recover within a few weeks, in about 5% of all cases of COVID-19, olfactory dysfunction persists for many months or years. During the recovery process, many experience parosmia, which is a condition in which everyday aromas become distorted and usually evoke a sense of disgust. Previous work has shown that a set of highly potent odorants in coffee can trigger these distortions. They fall into clusters of thiols, disulphides and pyrazines, and many (but not all) of these compounds are products of the Maillard reaction. In this work, we investigated another Maillard system and asked whether any of the Maillard-derived trigger molecules from coffee were also reported to be triggers in grilled chicken. GC-olfactometry was carried out by four participants and one non-parosmic expert to assess all the odour-active compounds in grilled chicken. Results revealed that indeed six triggers were found in common with coffee – all derived from the Maillard reaction. We postulate that the same few compounds may be responsible for distortions in many roasted, grilled and fried foods, and recommend that those suffering from parosmia avoid highly cooked foods.

Keywords: parosmia, anosmia, COVID-19, GC-Olfactometry, chicken, molecular triggers, olfactory dysfunction

Introduction

The impact of smell loss on quality of life is underestimated. Inability to smell gas or burnt food, or to smell intimate partners or the sufferer's own body odour, causes significant stress and anxiety, to the point where those who suffer can become clinically depressed [1]. Never have there been so many cases of anosmia (loss of sense of smell) as during the COVID-19 pandemic, when loss of “smell and taste” was recognised as an official symptom [2]. In fact, sudden loss of sense of smell [3] is so characteristic of SARS-CoV-2 infection, that it is by far the best predictor of COVID-19 [4], with an odds ratio (in the UK) of it being linked to COVID-19 of 6.5, whilst the odds ratio for all other symptoms was <2.5. Parma et al [5] showed that there was a mean drop of 89% in self-reported sense of smell, 76% in taste and 46% in chemesthesis during SARS-CoV-2 infection compared to before onset. Sudden onset of anosmia has been estimated to occur in about 50-60% of all cases of COVID-19 [6] but fortunately it is estimated that up to 80% of these will recover their sense of smell and taste within a few weeks [7]. Whilst the SARS-Cov-2 virus causes inflammation in the support cells in the olfactory epithelium [8], it is believed that for the majority of cases, the olfactory neurons remain intact and normal olfaction returns when the inflammation subsides. For the unfortunate 20% who do not recover their sense of smell within a few weeks, the problem is persistent and can last for many months or years and can be considered part of the Long-Covid suite of symptoms. This type of post-infectious anosmia is not new and is known to occur in other infections of the upper respiratory tract (influenza, common cold and sinus infections) but, until now, has been largely under-researched.

Recovery from post-infectious anosmia often starts 2-3-months after the initial loss of smell, when everyday smells become distorted and objectionable. These distortions can arise from foods, beverages, fragrances in personal care or household items, environmental aromas or even water [9]. This is known as parosmia, and those severely affected start to reject food, lose or gain weight, leading to clinical depression [9, 10]. Little is known about the underlying mechanisms, but it is generally believed that the virus causes widespread destruction of the olfactory sensory neurons, which need to regenerate before any sense of smell can return. The prevailing hypothesis for return of a distorted sense of smell is a random mis-wiring of the olfactory sensory neurons in the olfactory bulb, as they regenerate from the olfactory epithelium [11], sending unrecognised signals to the brain.

Several studies have collated lists of foods, drinks and personal care items that tend to trigger distortions [9, 12], and these indicate that coffee, meat, onions, garlic, egg, chocolate, toothpaste and shower gel are among the most frequently reported. Recently, Parker et al [11] proposed that many of the foods in question contained some of the most powerful odorants known, and set out to test the hypothesis that these potent odorants may be the origin of the distortions. Rather than using a time-consuming approach to determine individual molecular thresholds of a set of molecules selected by intelligent guesswork, GC-olfactometry was used to expose parosmic

participants (N=29) and non-parosmic participants (N=15) to a much wider selection of aroma compounds during a 30 min run time. Coffee was selected as a stable and convenient source of potent odorants, as it had the additional advantage that it is widely consumed and is one of the most frequently mentioned triggers. Parker et al. [11] showed that the parosmic group detected between them 30 different compounds at the odour port compared to the non-parosmic group who detected 60, and on average, each parosmic participant detected only 19 aroma compounds at the odour port, whereas the non-parosmic group detected twice as many (37). Of these 19 aroma compounds, on average only six were reported as being triggers. This finding was important as it demonstrated for the first time that the origin of the distortions was in the olfactory epithelium, indicating (at least in part) a peripheral mechanism rather than a purely central mechanism based in the integrative centres on the brain. Furthermore, the fact that two-thirds of the aroma compounds detected by the parosmic group were perceived as normal places constraints on the prevailing mis-wiring theory.

The most frequently reported trigger compounds identified in coffee fell into four different groups (Table 1). The most commonly reported (20/29) was 2-furanmethanethiol which has an exceptionally low threshold (0.005 µg/L) and is a character impact compound in coffee. The second most frequently reported compound was 2-ethyl-3,6-dimethylpyrazine which was reported 18/29 times as a trigger and has an odour threshold of 0.01 µg/L. The other 12 confirmed triggers were all known potent aroma compounds in coffee. Interestingly 4-ethylguaiacol and (E)-β-damascenone, which are also potent odorants in coffee, were perceived by some of the parosmic group but always with their characteristic descriptors (spicy and fruity respectively).

Table 1: Trigger compounds detected in coffee headspace by parosmic participants.

Thiols	Tri-substituted pyrazines	Disulphides	Methoxypyrazines
2-furanmethanethiol	2-ethyl-3,6-dimethylpyrazine	2-furanmethyl methyl disulphide	2-ethyl-3-methoxypyrazine
2-methyl-3-furanthiol	2,3-diethyl-5-methylpyrazine	2-methyl-3-furyl methyl disulphide	2-isobutyl-3-methoxypyrazine
3-methyl-2-butene-1-thiol	2-ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazine		2-isopropyl-3-methoxypyrazine
3-mercapto-3-methylbutanol	trimethylpyrazine		
3-mercapto-3-methylbutyl formate			

Sorted in decreasing order according to the number of times each compound was reported as a trigger.

Although coffee was selected for the initial study, in an analysis of parosmia social media groups [9], both onions and meat (which included beef, pork, chicken and lamb, but excluded bacon and sausages) were reported as frequently. Recognising that meat contains many of the compounds reported in Table 1, the aim of this experiment was to determine whether the same molecules triggered distortions in both coffee and grilled chicken.

Experimental

Ethics

This study (No 22/19) was approved by the University of Reading Research Ethics Committee.

Preparation of grilled chicken

A lean skinless chicken breast fillet was purchased at a local supermarket. Slices of 1 cm thickness were grilled for 3 min on both sides using a Cuisinart grill (Stamford, CT) set on high.

GC-Olfactometry and GC-MS of grilled chicken

Finely chopped grilled chicken (3 g) was placed in an SPME vial, equilibrated for 20 min at 55 °C, and the headspace extracted onto a triple phase SPME fibre (50/30 µm divinylbenzene/carboxen on polydimethylsiloxane (Supelco, Poole, UK)) for 20 min at 55 °C. After extraction, the volatiles were desorbed in a split/splitless injection port (280 °C) of an HP7890 GC from Agilent Technologies (Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with an Agilent HP-5 MSUi capillary (30 m, 0.25 mm i.d., 1.0 µm df) non-polar column, and coupled to a Series II ODO 2 GC-O system (SGE, Ringwood, Victoria, Australia). The temperature program was 40 °C for 2 min, then a rise of 5 °C/min up to 200 °C and 15 °C/min from 200 °C to 300 °C and the final temperature held for a further 19 min. Helium was used as carrier gas (2 mL/min). At the end of the column, the flow was split 1:1 between a flame ionisation detector (kept at 250 °C) and a sniffing port using two untreated silica-fused capillaries of the same

dimensions (1 m, 0.32 mm i.d.). The flow to the odour-port was diluted with a moist make up gas. One sample was also analysed on an Agilent 7890A Gas Chromatograph coupled to a 5975C series GC/MSD using the same column and a similar temperature program.

All the participants had already assessed coffee and were familiar with the procedure previously reported [11]. Four participants who had expressed their disgust for cooked chicken were invited to carry out the GC-Olfactometry procedure on grilled chicken. They were asked to describe the aromas as they eluted from the column, score their intensity on a general labelled magnitude scale (gLMS) and indicate whether the aroma was one that triggered parosmic distortions. One expert assessor also assessed a similar sample.

Results and discussion

Table 2: Trigger compounds detected in grilled chicken headspace by parosmic participants.

LRI ^a	Compound	Participant A	Participant B	Participant C	Participant D
674	unknown				parosmic meat (6)
867	2-methyl-3-furanthiol	onion (54 ^{*b})	rancid mouldy (25)		toast parosmic (6 [*])
906	methional (tentative)				parosmic lime (6)
912	2-furan-methanethiol	vegetable, terrible (35 [*])		cooked chicken (17 [*])	
1003	trimethylpyrazine			unpleasant (1 [*])	
1080	2-ethyl-3,6-dimethyl-pyrazine	not nice, lingers (35 [*])		popcorn unpleasant (9 [*])	
1088	2-ethyl-3,5-dimethyl-pyrazine		not nice cats pee (17 [*])	unpleasant (9 [*])	
1097	2-isopropyl-3-methoxy-pyrazine		not nice cats pee (17)		
1157	2,3-diethyl-5-methyl-pyrazine (and/or 3,5-dimethyl-1,2,4-trithiolane)	cats pee chocolate (51)			
1241	unknown	off veg (6)			

*Compounds that were reported as triggers for 4 different participants: participant A's combined gLMS score was the greatest and participants D's was the least. ^aLRI on a DB5 column, all compounds were detected by the expert assessor and have been reported in cooked chicken previously. ^bScore on a gLMS scale where 0 = no sensation, 1.4 = barely detectable, 6 = weak, 17 = moderate, 35 = strong, 51 = very strong and 100 = strongest imaginable sensation of any kind. *Compounds that were also reported as triggers by that participant in coffee.*

There was a significant overlap with coffee in the trigger compounds reported in grilled chicken. The two furanthiols, four trisubstituted pyrazines and one of the methoxypyrazines were all reported as triggers in both coffee and grilled chicken. Six of these are products of the Maillard reaction, and we anticipate that these compounds may also be responsible for the distortions experienced by many people with parosmia from anything roasted, grilled or fried (e.g. crisps, cocoa, peanut butter, marmite, toast).

Participant A reported the two furanthiols and one pyrazine as triggers, which had been previously reported as triggers in coffee. Interestingly participant A also reported a compound at LRI 1157 as cats pee, chocolate and very different to the descriptor at LRI 1088. It is possible that in grilled chicken, participant A was detecting 3,5-dimethyl-1,2,4-trithiolane which elutes at a similar LRI and has been reported in chicken previously as well 2,3-diethyl-5-methyl-pyrazine. The cyclic sulphur compound is more likely to give a cats pee note whereas the pyrazine would give a chocolate note. Further work needs to be carried out to carefully verify the identity of this trigger in grilled chicken for participant A. Participant B did not detect 2-methyl-3-furanthiol in coffee but did in chicken. We suggest that the higher concentrations present in meat, where it is a character impact compound, may

mean that this compound is above threshold in meat but not in coffee (for B). For participant C, all triggers reported for grilled chicken were also triggers in coffee. For participant D, all triggers were weak, but 2-methyl-3-furanthiol was reported as a trigger as it had been in coffee. The aroma at LRI 906 eluted a little early to be 2-furanmethanethiol, but may be methional, but this compound has not previously been reported as a trigger.

Although it is not the Maillard reaction per se which triggers distortions, it certainly generates many of the highly potent thiols and pyrazines which have been shown to be triggers in coffee and grilled chicken.

Conclusion

Many of the molecules that have previously been identified in coffee as triggers of the distortions, experienced by those with parosmia, were also identified as triggers in the headspace of grilled chicken. They are typical products of the Maillard reaction, whereas those compounds which are more specific to coffee were not found in chicken. It is likely that these Maillard-derived compounds may also act as triggers in other roasted, grilled or fried foods.

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